

Energy-based Residual for Collision Detection Using a Velocity Observer

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Abstract—Robot collision detection is addressed with an energy monitoring residual signal that uses only joint position measurements. The residual is evaluated by estimating joint velocity with a reduced-order observer. The observer uses in turn the momentum-based residual as additional input, acting as a virtual sensor of the external torque. We show the effectiveness of this method by comparing it in simulation with numerical differentiation of encoder measurements under nominal and uncertain conditions.

Index Terms—Collision detection, state estimation, physical human-robot interaction

I. INTRODUCTION

Collaborative robots operate by sharing the workspace with humans in dynamic and unstructured environments. Due to unpredictable human motion, collisions may occur, making it essential to detect them reliably for a prompt robot reaction.

In the robot collision event pipeline [1], we address here the problem of collision detection. Collisions are viewed as faulty behaviors of the robot actuating system that can be detected using a residual-based approach [2] that relies on an accurate dynamic model and only on proprioceptive sensors providing full information of the robot state. In the absence of tachometers, joint velocity is usually estimated via a finite difference method of encoder measurements. This method is compared with the use of a reduced-order observer [3] for velocity estimation. Our approach leads to a more accurate and robust detection of collision events.

II. METHODS

Consider a robot manipulator with n rigid joints. With the generalized coordinates $\mathbf{q} \in \mathbb{R}^n$, the robot dynamics in the possible presence of an external contact is

$$\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{q})\ddot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{C}(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}})\dot{\mathbf{q}} + \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{q}) = \boldsymbol{\tau}_m + \boldsymbol{\tau}_{ext} = \boldsymbol{\tau}_{tot}, \quad (1)$$

with the usual notation. Matrix \mathbf{C} factorizing the Coriolis and centrifugal terms is such that matrix $\dot{\mathbf{M}} - 2\mathbf{C}$ is skew-symmetric. The torque $\boldsymbol{\tau}_{tot}$ is the sum of the commanded torque $\boldsymbol{\tau}_m$ and of the unknown torque $\boldsymbol{\tau}_{ext} = \mathbf{J}_c^T(\mathbf{q})\mathbf{F}_{ext}$ generated by some contact wrench $\mathbf{F}_{ext} \in \mathbb{R}^6$.

In case of a collision, the total energy of the robot system $E = T(\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}}) + U(\mathbf{q})$, with $T = \frac{1}{2}\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{q})\dot{\mathbf{q}}$, is expected to change; it is possible then to detect a collision by monitoring this energy. A scalar residual $\sigma(t)$ is defined as [1]

$$\sigma(t) = k_\sigma \left(E - \int_0^t (\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \boldsymbol{\tau}_m + \sigma) dt \right), \quad k_\sigma > 0. \quad (2)$$

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Being its dynamics $\dot{\sigma} = k_\sigma (\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \boldsymbol{\tau}_{ext} - \sigma)$, the residual σ is identically zero in free motion and is excited by $\dot{\mathbf{q}}^T \boldsymbol{\tau}_{ext}$ upon a contact with robot in motion. Collision is detected ($\Pi(\sigma) = 1$) as soon as $|\sigma(t)| \geq \rho$, for a suitable threshold $\rho > 0$.

Figure 1: Block diagram of the proposed collision detection method.

To compute $\sigma(t)$, $\dot{\mathbf{q}}$ is required. If only \mathbf{q} is measured, joint velocity must be estimated. While a finite difference method could be used, we propose the use of a reduced-order observer to estimate the missing state information. Let $(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2) = (\mathbf{q}, \dot{\mathbf{q}})$ and $\mathbf{y} = \mathbf{x}_1$ be, respectively, the robot state and the measured output. The dynamics in state-space form is

$$\begin{aligned} \dot{\mathbf{x}}_1 &= \mathbf{x}_2 \\ \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{x}_1)\dot{\mathbf{x}}_2 &= -\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{x}_1, \mathbf{x}_2)\mathbf{x}_2 - \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{x}_1) + \boldsymbol{\tau}_{tot} \\ \mathbf{y} &= \mathbf{x}_1. \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

Consider the reduced-order observer with the structure [3]

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{y})\dot{\mathbf{z}} &= -\mathbf{C}(\mathbf{y}, \hat{\mathbf{x}}_2)\hat{\mathbf{x}}_2 - \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{y}) - k_0\mathbf{M}(\mathbf{y})\hat{\mathbf{x}}_2 + \hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_{tot} \\ \hat{\mathbf{x}}_2 &= \mathbf{z} + k_0\mathbf{y}, \quad k_0 > 0. \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

Under simple conditions, it is possible to obtain local exponential stability of the velocity estimation error $\boldsymbol{\epsilon} = \mathbf{x}_2 - \hat{\mathbf{x}}_2$. The observer (4) would require the same input $\boldsymbol{\tau}_{tot}$ as the robot system. While the command $\boldsymbol{\tau}_m$ is available (we use a computed torque control along a desired joint trajectory $\mathbf{q}_d(t)$), the unknown $\boldsymbol{\tau}_{ext}$ needs to be replaced by a proxy. To this end, we set $\hat{\boldsymbol{\tau}}_{tot} = \boldsymbol{\tau}_m + \mathbf{r}$, with the momentum-based residual [1]

$$\mathbf{r}(t) = \mathbf{K}_r \left(\hat{\mathbf{p}} - \int_0^t (\boldsymbol{\tau}_m + \mathbf{C}^T(\mathbf{q}, \hat{\mathbf{q}})\hat{\mathbf{q}} - \mathbf{g}(\mathbf{q}) + \mathbf{r}) dt \right), \quad (5)$$

where $\mathbf{K}_r > 0$ and the estimated velocity $\hat{\mathbf{q}} = \hat{\mathbf{x}}_2$ is used in place of $\dot{\mathbf{q}}$ to evaluate $\hat{\mathbf{p}} = \mathbf{M}(\mathbf{q})\hat{\mathbf{q}}$ and the quadratic velocity terms. The overall scheme is shown in Fig. 1.

Figure 2: Joint velocity estimation error $\epsilon = \dot{q} - \hat{q}$ using the reduced-order observer (top) and numerical differentiation of position (bottom). Spikes correspond to collisions.

III. NUMERICAL RESULTS

We report simulation results on a 3R spatial manipulator, with τ_{ext} generated by a pure collision force $F_{ext} = (f_{ext}, \mathbf{0})$ at the end-effector (the contact Jacobian J_c is a 3×3 matrix). During the planned trajectory, there are different phases:

- A: No external force applied. Robot moves to a rest state.
- B: End-effector moves in (y, z) -plane, with a force applied first along the x -direction, and then in the motion plane.
- C: Robot is at rest and no force is applied.
- D: A force with ramp profile is applied in x - and y -direction.
- E: End-effector starts moving in same (x, y) -plane of the external forces, which stop suddenly during robot motion.
- F: With robot at rest, a force is applied in x and y directions.
- G: Robot moves in the (x, z) plane with no external force.

Figure 2 compares the velocity estimation error ϵ using the reduced-order observer and via numerical differentiation of position ($\hat{q}(t_k) = (q(t_k) - q(t_{k-1})) / T_c$, with $T_c = 10$ ms). The method based on the observer performs consistently better.

This is also confirmed by the collision detection behavior shown in Fig. 3, where some spurious collisions (false positives) are detected using numerical differentiation, especially when an abrupt change of velocity occurs at low speed. One can notice that neither method detects some collisions (false negatives). This happens when no external power is generated at the instant of collision, i.e., $P_{ext} = \dot{q}^T \tau_{ext} = 0$. For the first collision in phase B, although $\dot{q} \neq \mathbf{0}$ and $\tau_{ext} \neq \mathbf{0}$, an orthogonality situation occurs at the end-effector level:

$$\dot{q}^T \tau_{ext} = \dot{q}^T J_c^T(q) f_{ext} = v_c^T f_{ext} = 0 \iff v_c \perp f_{ext}.$$

In phases D and F, $P_{ext} = 0$ simply because $\dot{q} = \mathbf{0}$. Indeed, as soon as $\dot{q} \neq \mathbf{0}$ around $t = 7$ s, a collision event is reported.

To investigate robustness to model uncertainties, the masses of the robot links are increased by 5% with respect to their nominal value. As shown in Fig. 4, the detection pattern based on the reduced observer is the same as in the nominal case of Fig. 3, while an additional incorrect detection occurs around $t = 8$ s when using numerical differentiation.

Figure 3: Comparison of collision detection performance using reduced-order observer or numerical differentiation for velocity estimation. From top: end-effector position p_{ee} , external force f_{ext} , residual σ with reduced-order observer and using numerical differentiation. In the last two plots, each correct collision detection is marked with a green star while incorrect ones with a black star.

Figure 4: Comparison of collision detection performance using reduced-order observer (top) or numerical differentiation (bottom) in case of a 5% mass uncertainty. Correct collision detections are marked with green stars, while incorrect ones with black stars.

IV. CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

We have combined an energy-based and a momentum-based residual in the context of robot collision detection, in order to overcome the lack of a direct measure of joint velocities. Extensive simulations (also in the accompanying video) have shown that classical numerical differentiation of position measurements is outperformed, both in nominal and uncertain conditions, by the use of a reduced-order observer for velocity estimation that feeds the evaluation of residual signals. We plan to validate this idea with experiments on a KUKA LWR4 robot.

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